

Social and educational AI for diversity: research on democratic values to develop artificial intelligence tools that guarantee access for all to educational tools and public services

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Abstract.

Innovations in Artificial Intelligence (AI) for social development must fulfill a dual objective: improving equal access to areas of public interest such as education, training and public services, as well as improving civic and democratic participation in the process of developing such innovations for all. It is necessary to develop models to articulate both dimensions of social design.

A particular case on these models is presented here concerning equal access for all people to public services, such as legal or educational procedures. This accessibility requires cognitive adaptability because legal or administrative language is very complex. For people with cognitive disabilities, and also for older people or citizens at risk of educational or social discrimination. AI can provide new tools to translate legal, administrative or educational texts into a simpler language. This becomes a multidisciplinary project if we want to respect ethical and legal consequences. It can only be achieved through civil and democratic engagement in two areas: 1) democratically selecting the type of texts and the type of translations needed and; 2) involving citizens, experts and non-experts, to produce and validate real examples of legal texts with cognitive adaptations to feed the AI algorithms used to learn how to translate those texts.

The social value of the presented model goes far beyond the design of a text simplification tool. The model aims to define participation and validation criteria to avoid the legal, social and equity biases present in the design of generative AI linguistic tools for social purposes.

Keywords: AI for Social Development, Responsible AI, Cognitive Adaptability, Easy-reading

1. State of the art

This research aims to develop innovations, policies and policy recommendations to apply and disseminate social AI tools to make administrative and educational processes more accessible. It will explore how to design a social participation system for the development of the necessary criteria for such an AI system. It is also proposed how to build on the AI designs themselves to support and improve this social participation. This means to reflect on a models of responsible AI that must take into account the requirements of people with special needs regarding their cognitive abilities to understand complex administrative, educational and legal texts.

1.1 Responsible AI

Responsible research and innovation (RRI) in artificial intelligence must meet a fundamental objective: everyone must share in the benefits of innovation [1, 2]. But innovation must also be democratic, i.e. everyone must have the possibility to participate in the decisions of the innovation process [3]. In particular, a democratic and inclusive model of participation and social innovation includes people with disabilities and people at risk of discrimination. It is not just about developing tools with a social purpose: equity must be included in design processes alongside the social function.

Instead of becoming an obstacle to RRI, this principle can become an asset if we involve citizens in the design process itself. [4, 5]. When it comes to technology development in AI, especially in machine learning tools that need a large amount of data to learn, the more people involved in the selection, elaboration or validation of the data and algorithms used to develop these tools, the better. [6].

The diversity of voices and criteria involved in these processes can be a first step towards achieving the goal of democratic innovation. However, the case of people with cognitive disabilities presents some particular aspects on how to articulate this participation for responsible innovation that will be studied in detail in this paper.

1.2 Diversity, cognitive abilities and easy-reading.

People with intellectual disabilities have limitations in their cognitive abilities, mainly in information processing: attention, perception, memory, problem solving, comprehension and analogies [7]. This does not mean that they can not cope with certain tasks. It only means that they have different cognitive abilities to do so. Therefore, we have to provide them an easier communicational environment to do the tasks. This is more important in the case of technological

environments where, nowadays, everybody share that problems [8]. About 30% of the world's population has difficulties in understanding some types of information. But this percentage is dramatically being increased since the amount of services, processes and tasks that are being mediated by advanced technologies, without human assistance, is prevalent for public and private interactions. We all have difficulties on those kind of environments because our cognitive abilities with interfaces, machines and computational services are very diverse regarding our education, age, or social and educational background. So we all need cognitive accessibility aids to help everyone to understand the environment and the information that surrounds us in an easy way, regardless of the capabilities, culture, language or background of each of them [9].

In the case of hard intellectual disabilities, the main difficulties of this people in their relationship with the environment are the difficulties in understanding information due to their memory, concentration or analytical problems. In particular, they have significant difficulties in understanding any type of written information, especially those that include acronyms, which require prior knowledge, or written information that presents excessive technicalities. Also, they have difficulties in coping with the unknown or dealing with unexpected events like being alone in an unfamiliar place, aggravated by difficulties in communicating with someone unfamiliar. This is related to their high level of sensitivity to stress. This can lead to a certain slowness in understanding instructions, as well as in making decisions [10].

The need of assistive tools for cognitive accessibility.

Intellectual disability is expressed in the relationship with the environment. Therefore, it depends both on the person himself and the barriers or obstacles around him. If we achieve an easier and more accessible environment, people with intellectual disabilities will have fewer difficulties [11]. Based on the above difficulties that people with intellectual disabilities have in their relationship with the environment, there are aspects and tools to alleviate these, and facilitate the understanding of the environment around us. Cognitive accessibility is related to the properties of environments, spaces, services, products, processes and texts that are easy to understand and/or use. And this is useful for everybody that has some kind of cognitive difficulties. An environment that meets adequate conditions of cognitive accessibility will allow all people who, permanently or temporarily, have difficulties in understanding, to access the understanding of the environment (educational centers, hospitals, leisure, etc.) and to benefit from adapted and adequate personal attention (services trained in attention to functional diversity). This kind of environment is mandatory to allow everybody to fully express their abilities and, finally, to participate in community life on equal conditions and as full citizens.

However, what determines the disability of people with low cognitive ability is the interaction with an environment unable to provide answers to their cognitive needs. Thus, when a space, public service and/or a product does not offer easily understandable information, people with intellectual disabilities encounter serious difficulties in accessing, using and enjoying them. And this includes educational centers and education itself.

In the case of physical difficulties or disabilities, the social model of disability advocates transforming the physical environment to make it more accessible. Ramps, acoustic and visual signs, markings and highlights on streets and pavements are transformations of the environment that serve as resources to make it more accessible and that last over time. However, in the case of cognitive disability or diversity, interactions take place with a cognitive environment that is highly changeable, in many cases on a minute-by-minute basis. We may translate some texts on an ongoing basis, or we may draw up lists and lists of translated signals. But there will always be other new texts or new signals, or informational messages of all kinds that need to be translated or adapted in real time. But this, the goal of creating a cognitive environment permanently adapted to everyone's needs is not feasible. Tools are needed to accompany the people who need them in their daily activities and to be able to translate texts, messages, signals or conversations simultaneously. AI offers countless options for such tools.

AI technologies offer the potential to remove some accessibility barriers. Computer vision could help blind people better perceive the visual world. Speech recognition and translation technologies already offer real-time automatic transcriptions for the hearing impaired. These are simple functions that used to be performed with great effort and are now made extremely easy and simple by AI. Unless there are many new applications, a long way is still to go regarding usability, utility and effectiveness of such assistive technology tools [12].

Taking into consideration the needs of users with disabilities can help technologists identify high-impact challenges whose solutions can advance the state of AI for all users; however, cognitive impairment has many different factors that require completely novel designs because the ethical challenges such as inclusivity, bias, privacy, error, expectation setting, simulated data, and social acceptability must be considered as a matter of justice and fairness. All people with intellectual disabilities have the possibility to progress if we give them the right supports to understand information in a language that they can cope with it. This will allow them to participate and use their spaces, services and products with the greatest possible autonomy. We need also to define processes of training on how to use and take care of the AI technologies for people with disabilities, how to use the appropriate dataset or algorithm at each case to get easy-to-understand documents, how to use those tools according to the rights of people with disabilities, etc. The case of legal texts is, maybe, the more interesting on this respect and the one that better justifies that AI is needed because it can accomplish the functions that no other technology or social process can achieve.

Legal texts and new frameworks of personal autonomy

Persons with disabilities have legal capacity on an equal footing with others, and with respect to them it is appropriate to adopt whatever measures are necessary to provide them with the support they may need in the exercise of that legal capacity, measures that must be guided by the principles of necessity and proportionality.

This is deduced from the International Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, made in New York on December 13, 2006, which Spain, for instance, has ratified and whose adaptation to our legal system is the origin of the legislative amendments contained in Law 8/2021, of June 2.

The first thing to point out is that the informing principle of this body of law, which is implemented in our civil and procedural rules, involves a change of concept in that, until now, our system was based on the substitution in the making of decisions affecting persons with disabilities, and now a new conception is adopted based on the respect for the will and preferences of the disabled person who, as a general rule, will be in charge of making his or her own decisions. In fact, under the new disability regime, only in situations where support cannot be provided in any other way, and only in the face of this situation of impossibility, will it be possible to provide it through representation in decision-making. The subjective scope of this regulation is also broadened, now also applicable to any person who needs this type of protection, and regardless of whether his or her disability situation has obtained any administrative recognition. The new regulation tries to attend not only to matters of a patrimonial nature, as up to now, but also to personal aspects, such as those related to decisions on the vicissitudes of the ordinary life -domicile, health, communications, etc.- of the disabled person.

People with disabilities have particular difficulty in reading court rulings. The new configuration of disability in the legal system, in which the regulatory change of Law 8/2021 on the reform of civil and procedural legislation states that they can be autonomous on court. But the adaptation and integration of people with disabilities is a pending task of Spanish Justice. In this sense, at present there is no general mechanism that allows the assistance and full participation of any person present in the courtroom, regardless of their physical or cognitive condition. In the seek of mechanisms for people with disabilities to exercise their right to participation and legal capacity. This kind of regulation demands very dynamic tools since each pronouncement is different. Also, each interaction on court may differ in so many ways. Therefore creating easy-reading texts needs to be done every time and at the best possible speed, but always producing texts that, despite simplicity, are written according to legal principles. We need cognitive criteria, but also legal criteria to evaluate texts.

In short, people with disabilities have the right to make their own decisions, a right that must be respected; it is, as the preamble to the law states, a "matter of human rights". Let us see how AI can help to implement those principles.

1.3 The main issue: need for validation

Up to now, AI tools with natural language processing (NLP) systems to produce generative adapted texts seems to be a good choice for the tasks of easy-reading to translate texts cognitively adapted so that people with intellectual disabilities, but also other groups such as the elderly, or those who do not know the language of the host country, can easily understand it.. But in the case of social and legal texts, is not enough to implement a series of guidelines that makes more easy the lexicon, semantics and even the organization and structure of the text. The validation of such a NLP tool for easy-reading requires attendance of a lists of guidelines from different institutions and points of view. And this validation tasks are very difficult and involve public participation at different levels. The methodology to decide how to implement that kind of public engagement on the very design of datasets, models and interfaces of AI easy-reading tools, is both a social and a technical problem that will be addressed on this research.

2 Methodology

The RRI framework aims to ensure that innovation is carried out in a socially responsible, inclusive and sustainable manner. A useful tool to achieve these objectives is participatory design, i.e., the active involvement of end users in all steps of the design of technological solutions. So that all steps, biases or ethical and social implications of such design are validated by stakeholders.

To apply this participatory model to the creation of an AI system that translates legal, administrative and educational texts into easy-to-read texts, we first need to identify the stakeholders. In our case, they all participate in the main task of feeding a machine learning system with the appropriate sample text, samples of pictographic languages, creative algorithms, bias avoidance algorithms, etc. This could be a four-step task

1. Creation of text samples to feed the machine learning systems.
2. Disability experts to validate the cognitive adaptability of easy-to-read texts
3. Ethics and social values experts to validate bias-free datasets and algorithms.
4. Legal experts to validate the legal accuracy of the texts produced.

This model involves social participation, including validation, in all four steps and, also, technological appropriation of the basis of the AI systems involved to refine and automate the participatory design process itself. To apply this model

within the RRI framework, it is necessary to justify the ethical, legal and cognitive reasons underlying the various validation steps of these four processes.

2.1 Cognitive experts and users.

Civil participation is needed to translate legal and administrative texts into easy-to-read texts. It is possible to find some legal texts translated into easy-to-read texts, but we need hundreds of them to create a specific and robust dataset. To do this, governments can contact social and civil associations that bring together entities working on behalf of people with intellectual or developmental disabilities and their families. It is necessary to create local and national areas specialized in Cognitive Accessibility composed of a group of experts in the adaptation of texts, documents or information to easy reading. Normally, most of these experts are the end users of these texts themselves, i.e., those with intellectual disabilities.

Adapting a legislative text to easy-reading is complex because it is necessary to express what the law says in words that are easier to understand and by giving examples, as there are many complicated and technical terms. In addition, it has been necessary to reorganize the structure and layout of the document differently, enlarging the font of the text or the line spacing, among others.

The people with intellectual disabilities that can participate in this process are responsible for validating the texts proposed by the cognitive expert. The function of validating consists of reviewing the adapted text and determining whether the document is comprehensible (both in terms of the terminology used, the organization of the text and the use of paratextual elements). These people, in addition to detecting aspects that could be improved, propose solutions to the adapter.

In addition to these adaptations, paratextual elements, such as pictographic symbols, or associating each title with a specific color, etc., must be used. These graphical issues are driven to complement the comprehension of the written text. Therefore, thinking in terms of AI models, adaptations are based on both NLP and graphic generators.

2.2 Experts and public participation to avoid social biases

Inclusivity of AI systems is related to their effectiveness for diverse user populations. There are many discussions regarding a lack of, age, gender and racial diversity in training data for AI systems, and how these biases can be exacerbated in the case of people with disabilities [13]. AI designs that use fairness approaches to avoid biases related to gender. There are many studies on how we should design AI solutions for people with disabilities avoiding biases [14]. Fairness may be a good methodology to do so [15, 16] since it is a main principle to be respected. But maybe it is not enough for cognitive disabilities because of its multiple variations and individual differences [14]. A more rich approach based on the differences instead of based on equality can be used in order to design individual interfaces suitable for each case. Only individual users, or very limited and specialized groups of users with cognitive disabilities can understand how a set of data or particular outcomes of an AI translation machine. Civil participation is needed, again, not only to work together with engineers to refine fairness of datasets and outcomes, but also to give insights on how to integrate it on the interfaces for interaction with those texts.

2.3 Steps to a legal accuracy: validation of legal translations.

Engagement of experts to validate translations from a legal point of view is usually forgotten when talking about easy-reading. They are specialist on the amendments to regulations made at national Civil Codes that must be followed. For instance, the title XI of book one of the Spanish Civil Code is rewritten and renamed "On support measures for persons with disabilities for the exercise of their legal capacity", in which voluntary measures -those that can be adopted by the person affected by the disability himself/herself- are strengthened, as a consequence of the principle that informs the reform.

The main support measure of judicial origin for persons with disabilities becomes the guardianship. It is intended to provide support in the exercise of legal capacity, along the lines of excluding, as far as possible, actions of a representative nature, and only in cases where necessary, and only exceptionally, representative functions may be attributed to the guardian.

In this case, expertise and public engagement is driven by some detailed principles that allow the selection of legal texts and legal procedures where easy-reading and, eventually, an AI system of translation, are needed. Those principles are:

- Informing principles: the support measures for persons of legal age or emancipated minors who need them for the proper exercise of their legal capacity will be intended to allow the full development of their personality and their legal development under conditions of equality, and only in the absence or insufficiency of the will of the person in question, may have a legal or judicial origin.

- Support measures of a voluntary nature are those established by the person with disability, in which he/she designates who should provide him/her with support and to what extent, which may be accompanied by the necessary safeguards to ensure respect for the will, wishes and preferences of the person.

And beyond the measures to support persons with disabilities, the Civil Code is modified with respect to other issues that have to do with them -nationality, their civil liability, the capacity to testament, the treatment of the legitimate and

the use of the habitual residence of the deceased as a legacy, their capacity to accept inheritances, their capacity to contract, the administration and extinction of the community of property in certain circumstances, the extinction of the partnership contract due to disability... -. The legal status of the person -in this case with capacity limitations- has many derivatives and affects a multiplicity of situations that require multiple regulation

This is the huge task that must be taking into account for a group of experts to feed datasets and learning algorithms. And, also, this has to be done for each regulatory framework on every country.

2.4 Integrating participation and evaluation as an AI solution.

There is a need to create a practical, policy-oriented definition of AI, a set of criteria for evaluating technologies according to cognitive diversity. We need to break down AI systems into constituent parts to allow users and experts on the various fields that we have defined for cognitive and legal easy-reading texts, to understand how to modify their outcomes. Technology needs easy ways to implement policy encounters between civil society groups, opening up AI reflection and repair work to multiple points of intervention. There are some proposals that goes far beyond simple reflection tools available to practitioners, and that involve a policy of community participation and activism [17].

Up to now, we have been defining the principle to design useful AI tools for cognitive disabilities, respecting fairness and legal requirements and avoiding biases. Now it is time to implement those principles on practical mechanisms on AI itself. The defined principles of civil participation on four levels of combined experts criteria, define a kind of collective cognition that have to be implemented with the aid of AI systems. This is complex social systems in which people and artificial text translations systems collaborate. Social uses of easy-reading translating systems open a very huge list of cases to be trained on the model. Could it be a way to automate this training. Some experiments claim that the cognitive capabilities of the experts humans can be copied ("cloned") and can be trained as collective (responsible) intelligence on models of generative adversarial networks [18]. The discriminator component of those models can be cloned to reproduce the four groups of experts criteria defined on our participation model. And can be trained in a way that includes one or more human and artificial discriminators working together. In this way, civil participation can act and collaborate in a group with its own cognitive artificial clones to speed up the process of neural network training and, at the same time, making it more accurate with human intervention.

Therefore, civil participation on this model can be also understood, from a technical point of view as a design fix including assessment learning machines designed specifically to evaluate different realms of principles, legal frameworks and social biases on generative/translation machines.

2.5 Technological participation needs more education (on AI)

The popular text generation development *ChatGPT* has shown us that it is possible to make a universal machine for all kinds of content and topics. But it has also shown us that in order to use the possibilities of a machine with as many functions as this one, a rather complicated interface is needed. Not only do we have countless options to choose from when ordering one type of text or another, but there are also different procedures to learn in order to really get the most out of it. If we want to use such a machine to facilitate the interaction of people with cognitive difficulties with their environment, we cannot do it with a tool that is difficult to use and understand.

The aim of our model is to design an AI machine for translation and generation of easy-reading texts with a claim to universality and, at the same time, easy to use and perfectly customisable. On the one hand, we need systems that provide translations from text to plain text or graphic language that support and help in all areas of public and official communication, and that do so in a way that is supervised by all these criteria. But, at the same time, we need very simple systems that do not introduce complex layers of optionality for people with cognitive difficulties. Therefore, such universal systems must be presented in individually adaptable interfaces, which are learnt and adjusted to the needs of each particular user, for each particular task. This will involve a further layer of supervision, and that is the control of interaction data with the AI system which will be very sensitive in terms of privacy. Let us not forget that we are talking about systems that will be used to assist the individual in really important matters. A kind of code of ethics is needed for these assistants similar to that of doctors or lawyers. The famous lists of AI laws that have been drawn up in some science fiction novels are going to become longer and longer, not least because these kinds of tools are going to be assistants to all of us in almost every aspect of our lives that requires cognitive processing.

This is probably the greatest difficulty of this type of proposal and an aspect to be improved in the present model. Technological training, both of the users and, above all, of the people who assist them in organizations, institutions, etc., is a key issue to guarantee that assistive technologies are really functional and not another hindrance for people with special needs.

3 Conclusion

AI can be applied for making educational and administrative processes more accessible for all. This innovations require policies and policy recommendations to apply and disseminate such social tools of AI.

It has been shown that this can be achieved, first, designing a civil participation process to engage citizens on the designing and use of AI tools for public services. Citizens engagement requires a participatory system on four main dimensions of the tasks:

- Involving experts for writing more easy to read texts and examples to feed learning AI systems
- Involving cognitive experts to validate the examples and creating analogies with graphical information
- Involving legal experts to validate and adjust biases and fairness of the system.
- Involving disability users and experts to validate final results and to create the interfaces and simple procedures to use NLP machines.

This will improve trust in democratic institutions and contribute to increase transparency, efficiency, accountability and legitimacy of public policies, allowing people to participate in the development of ethical standards for the use of these technologies. In addition, it will be a good move to improve educational tools for lifelong learning with AI models, and about AI models. Outreach, education and social participation will be integrated, measured and evaluated in innovative educational processes. All this is aimed at making educational and assistive technologies and content developed on AI accessible to all in the framework of responsible and social innovation.

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